

**MICROBIOLOGICAL FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT OF
CHILDHOOD BRONCHIAL ASTHMA**

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Abstract: Bronchial asthma is one of the most common chronic non-communicable diseases in childhood, affecting 5–10% of school-aged children and adolescents, as well as 1–18% of the population in different countries. There are significant global differences in the prevalence of asthma symptoms among children, with variations between countries reaching up to 13-fold. According to estimates by the World Health Organization, 339 million people worldwide suffer from asthma, and 461,000 deaths caused by this disease have been recorded. According to data from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, the overall economic burden of bronchial asthma in school-aged children amounts to approximately 2 billion dollars per year. These costs include direct medical expenses such as medications, hospitalization, outpatient treatment, and emergency medical care, as well as reduced parental productivity due to children missing school because of bronchial asthma exacerbations.

Keywords: *bronchial asthma, prevention, morbidity, children, allergy.*

Аннотация: Бронхиальная астма — одно из наиболее распространенных хронических неинфекционных заболеваний в детском возрасте, поражающее 5–10% детей школьного возраста и подростков, а также 1–18% населения в разных странах. Существуют значительные глобальные различия в распространенности симптомов астмы среди детей, причем различия между странами достигают 13-кратного значения. По оценкам Всемирной организации здравоохранения, 339 миллионов человек во всем мире страдают астмой, и зарегистрировано 461 000 смертей, вызванных этим заболеванием.

Согласно данным Центров по контролю и профилактике заболеваний, общее экономическое бремя бронхиальной астмы у детей школьного возраста составляет приблизительно 2 миллиарда долларов в год. Эти затраты включают прямые медицинские расходы, такие как лекарства, госпитализация, амбулаторное лечение и неотложная медицинская помощь, а также снижение

производительности труда родителей из-за пропуска детьми школы в связи с обострениями бронхиальной астмы.

Ключевые слова: *бронхиальная астма, профилактика, заболеваемость, дети, аллергия.*

Introduction

Bronchial asthma is a complex and multifactorial chronic disease of the respiratory tract, clinically characterized by wheezing, shortness of breath, and cough. These symptoms may occur due to exposure to various allergens or infections. Diagnosis is based on clinical symptoms associated with variable expiratory airflow limitation. It has been proven that both genetic predisposition and environmental factors are involved in the pathogenesis of asthma. Increasing evidence suggests that asthma may begin to develop at an early age.

The concept of the evolutionary origins of health and disease originates from the hypothesis proposed over 30 years ago by Professor David Barker, who studied how environmental influences such as nutrition, medications, diseases, the microbiome, and stress interact with genotypic changes throughout life. This may explain the complex onset of individual risk for non-communicable diseases such as asthma in children and adults and may also enable the development of therapeutic interventions during pregnancy and early childhood to improve adult health outcomes.

Human lung development begins at approximately the 4th week of gestation and includes four distinct histological stages. In addition, recent studies have shown that a certain degree of alveolarization may continue into early adulthood. The completion of postnatal lung development explains why genetic and environmental disturbances occurring after birth may lead to long-term structural and functional lung impairment, increasing susceptibility to respiratory diseases later in life.

Main part

Preterm birth before 32 weeks of gestation has been associated with an increased risk of bronchial obstruction in both preschool children and those aged 7–11 years [1]. In addition, several studies have shown that rapid postnatal weight gain or low birth weight in preterm infants are independent risk factors for adverse respiratory outcomes [2]. A meta-analysis of 31 European studies including 147,252 children under the age of 10 confirmed that shorter gestational age is associated with an increased risk of developing bronchial asthma [3].

The exact gestational age threshold required to reduce asthma risk has not been clearly defined in the literature. A large Swedish study including 622,616 individuals showed that only extreme preterm birth (<28 weeks) was associated with asthma development in young adulthood (25.5–35 years) [4]. In a Swedish national cohort of

1,100,826 children, Vogt et al. [5] reported that reduced asthma risk was positively associated with increasing gestational age from 6 to 19 years of age, even among term-born children.

Bronchopulmonary structural immaturity caused by preterm birth during a critical stage of fetal development, or lung injury resulting from neonatal treatment, is one of the main causes of chronic lung disease [6].

The duration of asthma risk associated with preterm birth remains unclear. The impact of preterm birth on respiratory symptoms is more pronounced in early childhood [5] and gradually decreases with age [4].

In conclusion, long-term studies involving large and homogeneous populations are needed to better understand the impact of preterm birth on lung function and asthma development at different stages of life.

Birth characteristics

It has been widely shown that children born in the cold season have a higher risk of developing bronchial asthma compared to those born in spring. This may be associated with higher levels of lymphocytes and leukocytes, as well as increased concentrations of anti-inflammatory cytokines [7].

The mode of delivery may also influence the development of asthma and allergies later in life. In the past two decades, the rate of cesarean section has significantly increased, which has been linked to a higher risk of asthma in children [8]. Furthermore, a meta-analysis of 13 studies including 887,960 individuals showed that children born by cesarean section have a higher risk of developing asthma up to the age of 12 [9].

The increased risk of immune-related diseases associated with cesarean delivery, including asthma and respiratory infections [10], is likely related to the absence of physiological stress and immune regulatory processes that normally occur during vaginal birth. Disruption of this natural process alters early immune programming of the neonatal gut microbiota. In addition, cesarean delivery affects microbial diversity: newborns are colonized by maternal skin flora rather than vaginal microbiota [11].

As noted above, microbiota composition is strongly influenced by delivery mode, as well as host genetics and immunity, diet, infections, antimicrobial use, and family environment. Children born vaginally show intestinal colonization dominated by Lactobacilli and greater microbial diversity compared to those born by cesarean section [12].

The concept that microbial metabolites or immunomodulatory molecules produced in the gut can migrate to the lungs and exert biological effects is known as the “gut–lung axis” [13]. However, current evidence remains incomplete and contradictory; future well-designed studies may clarify this relationship.

In addition, increased risk of obesity and delayed breastfeeding are other factors associated with Crohn's disease, which may indirectly influence asthma development.

Breastfeeding

Breast milk is considered the optimal source of nutrition for full-term infants during the first six months of life [14]. It is an immunologically active biological fluid containing numerous compounds that support infant growth and immune system development [15].

Currently, evidence regarding the relationship between breastfeeding and asthma development is limited and inconsistent, partly because randomized allocation to breastfeeding or formula feeding groups is ethically impossible. In addition, variability in study design and differences in breast milk composition may introduce bias in observational studies [16].

A meta-analysis by Dogaru et al. including 117 studies showed that the protective effect of breastfeeding against asthma is strongest in the first two years of life. During this period, wheezing is often associated with respiratory infections and does not always indicate later asthma [17].

The persistence of a protective effect in school-age children, although weaker, supports the hypothesis that early-life respiratory infections may contribute to later asthma development. A systematic review and meta-analysis showed that longer duration and exclusivity of breastfeeding are associated with reduced asthma risk, although no statistically significant effect was observed in children aged ≥ 7 years [18]. As children grow older, the complex interaction between different risk factors becomes more evident. One recent study found that by age 6, statistical significance was observed only in children without a family history of asthma [19].

Neonatal jaundice

A recent meta-analysis showed that children who experienced neonatal jaundice and received phototherapy had a higher risk of developing childhood-onset asthma [19]. The pathogenesis of this association remains unclear. It is hypothesized that cumulative exposure to unconjugated bilirubin and secondary DNA damage from phototherapy may disrupt the Th1/Th2 balance [20]. A subsequent Th2-dominant immune response may promote allergic disease development [21]. However, the association between neonatal jaundice and childhood asthma is likely weaker than previously assumed.

Conclusion

Bronchial asthma is one of the most common chronic diseases of childhood worldwide and is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in both children and adults. Risk factors for asthma development include genetic, environmental,

socioeconomic, and clinical factors, ultimately leading to airway hyperresponsiveness, bronchial inflammation, and airway remodeling.

Asthma exacerbations often require hospitalization; therefore, poorly controlled asthma in children may result in sleep disturbances due to nocturnal symptoms, reduced school attendance due to hospitalization, and limited participation in sports due to fear of symptom exacerbation. Frequent asthma attacks also affect families, as parents may need to miss work and lose income to care for their child. Despite many new and modern treatment approaches, it is important to emphasize again that asthma attacks in both children and adults can be significantly reduced by identifying and managing modifiable risk factors.

Asthma prevention education should include proper use of inhalation devices with spacers, adherence to prescribed therapy, early recognition of bronchial obstruction and worsening control, the importance of physical activity and diet, and elimination of modifiable environmental risk factors in the immediate surroundings.

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